

Soft vs. hard power impact on UN voting on Ukraine

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Abstract. - We analyse the importance of a wide range of factors influencing the voting behaviour of countries in favour of Russia in the UN resolution (A/RES/ES-11/6¹) on March 2 2023. We group factors into ‘economic influence’, ‘defence cooperation’ and ‘soft power’, besides the standard country-level control variables, and formulate hypotheses on their expected impact according to extant theory and evidence. We include economic, political and military ties with Russia and China (as a major supporter of Russia) in a multivariate regression analysis. Our results show Russia’s hard power at work: the probability of voting in favour of Russia was significantly higher for countries receiving Russian aid, Russian foreign direct investment, arms imports and defence cooperation from Russia. At the same time, China’s soft power also exerted considerable influence on voting patterns, to the extent that Belt and Road Initiative participation and Global South significantly increased the probability of voting in favour of Russia.

Keywords: Belt and Road Initiative, Defence cooperation agreements; foreign aid; Global South, multinomial regressions; Russia-Ukraine war; hard power; soft power; United Nations General Assembly; voting behaviour

JEL: D72, F35, F50, F51

1. Introduction

Exactly one year since the Russian invasion of Ukraine, the U.N. General Assembly approved a nonbinding resolution (A/RES/ES-11/6²) on March 2 2023 that calls for Russia to end hostilities in Ukraine and withdraw its forces. Among its 193-members, 141 members voted in support of the resolution, 7 voted against, 32 abstained and 13 were absent. Despite the vast majority of supporting votes, those 52 including rejections and neutral positions have attracted considerable attention, as 45 out of 52 are from the world’s poorest and least industrialised countries, which is increasingly labelled as Global South.³

This voting behaviour inspired speculation about new alliances emerging in the Global South, led by China, the largest in the group, notably adopting a position of neutrality in the conflict. China’s deep relations with a vast number of countries might have influenced their votes. The 109 countries out of 133 in the Global South that are part of the China’s Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) – a comprehensive programme of bilateral economic and political relationships that China has built since 2013 as a canvas for its economic diplomacy and a major tool of soft power – may have looked at China’s abstention and decided not to cast a vote against Russia, for fear of jeopardising their own bilateral relations with China.

¹ Available at [N2306307.pdf \(un.org\)](#).

² Available at [N2306307.pdf \(un.org\)](#).

³ Our classification of countries in the Global South, as opposed to “Global North” is taken from the United Nations Finance Center for South-South Cooperation, who maintains arguably the world’s most reputable and reliable list of Global South countries. It is available here <https://worldpopulationreview.com/country-rankings/global-south-countries>.

Research on the reasons why some countries consistently declined to condemn Russia's invasion of Ukraine at the United Nations General Assembly's first emergency session since 1997 has so far focused on the role of economic, military, political, geographic, and historical ties with Russia only (Farzanegan and Gholipour, 2023). Evidence shows that those countries are among those that have defense cooperation agreements with Russia, have a longer history of leftist governments, are major recipients of Russian aid, have political similarities with Russia, and have no history of war with the Soviet Union.

In this paper we contribute to the empirical literature on determinants of UN voting patterns by empirically analysing the importance of a wider range of factors in resolution A/RES/ES-11/6 held on March 2 2023. We group factors into 'economic influence', 'defence cooperation' and 'soft power', besides the standard country-level control variables, and formulate hypotheses on their expected impact according to extant theory and evidence. Besides economic, political and military ties with Russia, we also include economic and political relations with China, to the extent that the two countries have enjoyed close relations militarily, economically, and politically, while supporting each other on various global issues. Since early February 2022 China and Russia have forged a friendship with "no limits", although their bilateral strategic partnership does not constitute a formal alliance.

Using a multivariate regression analysis, we test the influence of various groups of factors on the probability of countries' voting in favour of Russia in resolution A/RES/ES-11/6 held on March 2 2023. We expect both hard power (i.e. economic and military ties) and soft power to exert influence on countries voting patterns⁴. On the one hand, the hard power of economic relations with Russia and with China through trade and investment linkages, combined with military and defence cooperation agreements or plurilateral frameworks led by Russia and China, are expected to exert a significant influence on partner countries. At the same time, hard power is increasingly complemented by a range of soft power tools implemented over the last decade to gain consensus among partner countries, either bilaterally or plurilaterally.

Our results confirm previous research on the strong influence of Russian defence and military cooperation: the probability of voting in favour of Russia was significantly higher for countries receiving Russian aid, Russian FDI, arms imports and defence cooperation from Russia. Except for Russian FDI, other channels of economic influence in the form of strong trade ties were not influential factors. Neither were economic ties with China. Instead, soft power by China exerted considerable influence on voting patterns, to the extent that BRI participation and Global South significantly increased the probability of voting in favour of Russia. As regards host country factors, poor and landlocked countries show higher probability of voting in favour of Russia.

The rest of the paper is organised as follows. Section 2 provides some description of countries' votes on resolution A/RES/ES-11/6 against Russia. Section 3 reviews the literature on determinants of UN voting. Section 4 describes different factors influencing UN voting patterns and the expected sign of their impact. Section 5 performs a multivariate analysis of UN resolution A/RES/ES-11/6 on Ukraine and describes the results. Section 6 concludes.

⁴ According to Nye (2008), hard power is the use of military and economic means to influence the behaviour or interests of other political bodies. Hard power contrasts with soft power, which comes from diplomacy, culture and history. Hard power involves "the ability to use the carrots and sticks of economic and military might to make others follow your will".

2. Countries' votes on resolution A/RES/ES-11/6 calling for Russia to end hostilities

Exactly one year since the Russian invasion of Ukraine, the U.N. General Assembly approved a nonbinding resolution (A/RES/ES-11/6⁵) on March 2 2023 that calls for Russia to end hostilities in Ukraine and withdraw its forces. Among its 193-members, 141 members voted in support of the resolution, exceeding the two-thirds threshold needed to pass (among these are the 31 NATO members). Seven members — Belarus, North Korea, Eritrea, Mali, Nicaragua, Russia and Syria — voted against. The remaining 45 either abstained (32 members, including China, India, Iran and South Africa) or were absent (13). Despite the vast majority of supporting votes, those 52 including rejections and neutral positions have attracted considerable attention, as 45 out of 52 are from the world's poorest and least industrialised countries, which is increasingly labelled as Global South⁶ (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Vote distribution within Global North (0) and Global South (1)

Source: own computation on UN data

This voting behaviour has inspired speculation about new alliances emerging in the Global South, inspired by China and India, the largest in the group, notably adopting a position of neutrality in the conflict. Some point to Russia's push to capitalize on disillusionment with the United States to win sympathy in the Global South, as the case of Iran and North Korea clearly show but there may be other reasons, including economic ones. Most notably, Russia's trade partners in Asia, such as India, have seen their trade with Russia balloon since the invasion, with a 400 growth in bilateral trade in India's case. India's position is particularly illuminating as it seems it somehow refuses to risk its relationship with Russia, on which it depends for military supplies (with 70% of its military equipment coming from Russia) and recently benefits from discounted Russian oil. At the same time, India may want to avoid escalating tensions at its borders with China, where tens of thousands of Chinese troops are stationed there.

⁵ The text is available at [N2306307.pdf \(un.org\)](https://www.un.org/News/Press/docs/2023/03/2306307.pdf).

⁶ Our classification of countries in the Global South, as opposed to "Global North" is taken from the United Nations Finance Center for South-South Cooperation, who maintains arguably the world's most reputable and reliable list of Global South countries. It is available here <https://worldpopulationreview.com/country-rankings/global-south-countries>.

Other countries in the Global South may also have looked at China’s abstention and their own bilateral relations which China, for example through their participation in China’s Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), a comprehensive programme of bilateral economic and political relationships that China has built since 2013 as a canvas for its economic diplomacy and a major tool of soft power. In fact, 109 out of 133 countries in the Global South are part of the BRI (Table 1). Therefore, it comes as no surprise that voting patterns in the UN resolution condemning Russian invasion of Ukraine are very similar when grouping countries into Global South vs. Global North and BRI vs. non-BRI (Figure 2).

Table 1 Global South and BRI

BRI dummy	globalSouth		Total
	0	1	
BRI	36	109	145
Non-BRI	22	24	46
Total	58	133	191

Source: own computation on UN data

Many observers and the media offered some hints on why many countries voted in favour of Russia (either directly by rejecting the resolution, or indirectly by abstaining or being absent). For example, the Washington Post has reported about the changing voting behaviour by Mali about the situation in Ukraine: “Mali, which had on two previous occasions abstained from voting on U.N. resolutions on Ukraine, shifted its position to vote against this week’s resolution, coming out in support of Russia. Its government has been the recipient of renewed Russian military assistance as the Kremlin seeks to expand its global influence. Earlier this month [February 2023], Malian authorities welcomed Russian Foreign Minister Sergei Lavrov on a visit aimed at strengthening security and economic cooperation.”⁷

Figure 2 Vote distribution within BRI and non-BRI countries

Source: own computation on UN data and BRI participation (<https://eng.yidaiyilu.gov.cn/>)

⁷ [Countries that abstained from voting on U.N. Ukraine resolution: list - The Washington Post](#)

3. Background literature

The literature on country voting behaviour in the UN (e.g., Alexander and Rooney 2019; Bailey, Strezhnev, and Voeten 2017; Che, He, and Zhang 2021; Dreher, Nunnenkamp, and Thiele 2008; Dreher and Jensen 2013; Dreher et al. 2018a, 2018b; Keohane 1967; Lektzian and Biglaiser 2022; Mosler and Potrafke 2020; Wittkopf 1973; Woo and Chung 2018; Yan and Zhou 2021) mainly focused on countries' political support of China and the United States in the UN. Most of extant studies find that bilateral trade and foreign aid are the most important determinants of voting patterns in the UN. Recently, Farzanegan and Gholipour (2023) empirically analysed the voting behaviour in the resolution A/RES/ES-11/1 condemning Russian invasion of Ukraine, taken at the UNGA on March 2, 2022. They test a number of economic, military, political, geographic and historical factors that may have influenced countries' votes in favour of Russia. They find that the probability of voting in favor of Russia is significantly and robustly higher in countries that have defense cooperation agreements with Russia, have a longer history of leftist governments, are major recipients of Russian aid, have political similarities with Russia, and have no history of war with the Soviet Union.

Over the course of the year running since the Russian invasion of Ukraine, an additional channel of influence on countries' positions on the war in Ukraine has come from China's own indirect support of Russia, in the form of an 'endless friendship' confirmed by the PRC abstention in the UN Resolution against Russia in 2022. Similarly to what happened at the UNHCR⁸, China's deep relations with a vast number of countries might have influenced their votes. In order to explore this, and drawing on the above literature, this note tries to test the importance of a wider range of factors grouped into those that exert influences through economic, trade and investment linkages, those that exert influence through military alliances and cooperation, and last but not least, those that gain international support through diplomatic ties and plurilateral initiatives, one of China's masterpiece activities to gather consensus abroad.

4. Factors influencing countries' voting on Ukraine

This section sets out our hypotheses on the determinants of UN voting patterns on resolution A/RES/ES-11/6, based on theory and previous research. Factors are grouped into three categories: economic influence, defence cooperation and soft power (Table 2). Host country factors as control variables include per capita GDP and landlockedness⁹.

3.1 Economic influence

Economic influence includes trade and foreign direct investment (FDI), from Russia as well as from China, who has officially sealed an unconditional friendship with Russia on the eve of the Russian invasion of Ukraine, and indirectly supported Russia, most notably by abstaining from voting on resolution (A/RES/ES-11/1) on March 2, 2022 condemning Ukraine invasion. The extant literature shows that bilateral international trade linkages are important factors influencing the UN General Assembly voting for two reasons: (1) trade interdependence might create similar preferences on certain

⁸ <https://www.eastasiaforum.org/2023/01/19/beijings-bri-influence-over-the-un-human-rights-council/>

⁹ For a broad overview of the development costs of being landlocked, see https://www.un.org/ohrrls/sites/www.un.org.ohrrls/files/ldcs_publications/dev-costs-of-landlockedness.pdf

topics between partner countries (Dreher, Nunnenkamp, and Thiele 2008); (2) strong bilateral trade relationships between countries might create fears of losing access to source and destination markets (Dreher, Nunnenkamp, and Thiele 2008; Keohane 1967).

Table 2 Explanatory variables

Category	Subgroup	Variable	Source
Economic influence	Trade ties with Russia	Export to Russia (share of a country's export to Russia on total exports)	UNCTAD
		Import from Russia (share of a country's import from Russia on total imports)	UNCTAD
		Oil imports from Russia (2017-2021)	UNCTAD
		Arms imports from Russia	https://sipri.org/databases/armstransfers
		Free Trade Agreement (FTA) with Russia	WTO
	Trade ties with China	Export to China (share of a country's export to China on total exports)	UNCTAD
		Import from China (share of a country's import from China on total imports)	UNCTAD
		Free Trade Agreement (FTA) with China	WTO
	Investment relations with Russia	Foreign Direct Investments (FDI) from Russia	UNCTAD and Central Bank of Russia
		Bilateral Investment Treaty (BIT) with Russia	WTO
Defence cooperation		Shanghai Cooperation Organisation (SCO) member	http://eng.sectsc.org/docs/about/faq.html
		Defence Cooperation Agreement (DCA) with Russia	Kinne (2018)
		NATO membership	nato.int
Soft power		Belt and Road Initiative (BRI)	https://eng.yidaiyi.lu.gov.cn/
		Global South	https://worldpopulationreview.com/country-rankings/global-south-countries
		Russian aid	Central Bank of Russia

Trade ties with Russia. As imports from Russia and exports to Russia may exert different impacts on voting decisions, in this paper we separately test the importance of imports from Russia (measured as the share of a country's import from Russia on total imports) from that of exports to Russia (measured as the share of a country's export to Russia on total exports). Moreover, as many countries import some strategic products such as energy commodities (oil and gas), unprocessed food (mainly cereals), and arms from Russia, we also include oil imports from Russia and arms imports from Russia. Finally, we account for the presence of a Free Trade Agreement with Russia, a factor that may facilitate bilateral trade flows.

The extant literature suggests that both import and export ties should have a positive impact on the probability to vote in favour of (or at least not against) Russia.

Trade ties with China. As in the case of trade ties with Russia, we separately test the importance of imports from China (measured as the share of a country's import from China on total imports) from that of exports to China (measured as the share of a country's export to China on total exports). We also account for the presence of a Free Trade Agreement with China, a factor that may facilitate bilateral trade flows and is a signal of closer economic relations with China.

Investment ties with Russia. According to previous research, foreign direct investment may exert either a positive or a negative influence on voting behavior of recipient countries. Dreher and Sturm (2012) argue that investment ties might increase (or decrease) the probability of voting with the partner country. On the one hand, countries recipient of FDI may develop similar preferences on certain topics with the investing country, for fear of losing inward investment. For example, Raess, Ren, and Wagner (2017) show that China's outward FDI is positively related to recipient countries' political realignment toward China. On the other hand, investment ties might create feelings of exploitation in the recipient countries and could thus give rise to voting against major economic powers (Dreher and Sturm, 2012). In this paper, we test the impact on voting behavior of recipient countries of FDI from Russia. Our expectations on the effect of FDI is ambiguous because on the one hand the majority of recipient countries are high income economies and/or NATO members (all of which voted against Russia), while on the other hand landlocked countries (among which are some of the poorest countries in the world) receive on average twice as much FDI as non-landlocked ones, which suggests that FDI from Russia may not necessarily and primarily follow a market-seeking motivation (as suggested by Kalotay and Sulstarova, 2010). We also include the presence of a Bilateral Investment Treaty (BIT) with Russia, a signal of closer economic relations with China, which should positively influence UN voting behaviour in favour of Russia.

3.2 Defence and military cooperation

Defence and military cooperation include with Russia through Defence Cooperation Agreements and more broadly within the Asian continent, covered by the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO), a Eurasian political, economic, international security and defence organization established by China and Russia in 2001 as an anti-NATO bloc. SCO is the world's largest regional organization in terms of geographic scope and population, covering approximately 60% of the area of Eurasia.

Defence Cooperation Agreement (DCA) with Russia. DCAs are "formal bilateral agreements that establish institutional frameworks for routine defence cooperation." (Kinne, 2018; p.803). Research on the impact of military and defence cooperation on country voting behaviour in the UN has so far provided mixed results. On the one hand, some results confirm the Arms for Influence theory according to which superpower military aid is as a way to buy cooperation from the recipient state (Keohane and Nye 1977; Sullivan, Tessman, and Li 2011). For example, Lai and Morey (2006) find that dependence on US military aid leads to a greater likelihood of UN nondemocratic members voting in favour of the US. On the other hand, Sullivan, Tessman, and Li (2011) show that higher levels of military aid produce more defiant behaviour in aid recipient nations.

Shanghai Cooperation Organisation (SCO). We include membership in the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) as a possible positive factor in supporting Russia over the war with Ukraine. SCO

includes eight Member States (China, India, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Russia, Pakistan, Tajikistan, and Uzbekistan), four Observer States interested in acceding to full membership (Afghanistan, Belarus, Iran, and Mongolia) and six “Dialogue Partners” (Armenia, Azerbaijan, Cambodia, Nepal, Sri Lanka, and Turkey). In 2021, the process of full membership of Iran started and Egypt, Qatar, and Saudi Arabia joined the dialogue partners (United Nations 2022b).

3.3 Soft power

Soft power factors in our data include Russian aid, a major determinant of influence according to the extant research, and two plurilateral initiatives involving both Russia and China, namely the Belt and Road Initiative and the Global South.

Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) and Global South. As described and documented in Section 2, BRI and Global South largely overlap with one another: 109 out of 133 countries in the Global South are part of the BRI. Voting patterns in the UN resolution condemning Russian invasion of Ukraine are very similar when grouping countries into Global South vs. Global North and BRI vs. non-BRI. Therefore, both BRI participation and Global South should positively influence countries’ voting behaviour.

Russian aid. According to previous research, Russian aid is one of the most important factors influencing the voting behaviour of recipient countries in favour of Russia (Alexander and Rooney, 2019); Che, He, and Zhang, 2021; Dreher, Nunnenkamp, and Thiele, 2008). Therefore, we expect a positive influence of the amount of aid from Russia on the probability that recipient countries vote in favour of the donor country.

4 A multivariate analysis of UN resolution A/RES/ES-11/6 on Ukraine

To test the importance of the above factors on the UN resolution on Ukraine, we run a set of multivariate regressions of UN votes.

4.1 Dependent variable

Our dependent variable is a categorically distributed dependent variable that can take three different possible outcomes, namely Approve, Reject or Neutral (abstain or absent)¹⁰. Given our multiclass dependent variable, we apply a multinomial logistic regression¹¹ to predict the probabilities that a country votes in favour of the resolution against Russia (Approve), or rejects the resolution against Russia (Reject), or remains neutral because it either abstains from the vote or is absent (Neutral).

The probability that country i will select alternative j is:

$$p_{ij} = p(y_i=j) = \frac{\exp(w_i y_j)}{\sum_{k=1}^m \exp(w_i y_k)}$$

¹⁰ Country votes are collected from the UN Digital Library at <https://digitallibrary.un.org/>

¹¹ Multinomial logistic regression is used when the dependent variable in question is nominal (equivalently *categorical*, meaning that it falls into any one of a set of categories that cannot be ordered in any meaningful way) and for which there are more than two categories. This model is a generalization of the binary logit model.

The probabilities for choosing each alternative j (with $j=0$ for Approve, $j=1$ for Neutral, $j=2$ for Reject) sum up to 1 ($\sum_{j=0}^2 p_{ij} = 1$)¹². As one set of coefficients needs to be normalized to zero to estimate the other two models, we select as a baseline the vote Approve (the biggest category, i.e. $y_i=0$). Coefficient interpretation for alternative $j=1, 2$ is as follows: in comparison to the baseline case ($j=0$), an increase in the independent variable makes the selection of alternative $j = 1, 2$ more or less likely.

4.2 Explanatory variables

As described in Section 3, we consider a set of explanatory factors among independent variables (Table 2), grouped into three categories: economic influence, defence cooperation and soft power. Descriptive statistics and pairwise correlations of continuous variables are respectively in Table 3 and 4.

Table 3 Summary statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Export intensity with China	182	11.35533	15.46578	0	88.14
Export intensity with Russia	163	1.696012	4.683948	0	47.02
Import intensity with China	190	15.84432	10.61695	.28	96.89
Import intensity with Russia	167	3.553713	7.315522	0	55.66
Oil import from Russia	191	1.643979	5.351749	0	58.9
Arms import from Russia	191	355.1518	1460.296	0	16587
FDI from Russia	191	1450.257	5252.982	0	43253
Per capita GDP	191	13055.76	18644.21	113	116360

Table 4 Pairwise correlations

	Arms import from Russia	Export intensity with Russia	Export intensity with China	Import intensity with China	Import intensity with Russia	Oil import from Russia	FDI from Russia	Per capita GDP
Arms import from Russia	1							
Export intensity with Russia	0.0145	1						
Export intensity with China	-0.0011	-0.0556	1					
Import intensity with China	0.1056	-0.0343	0.3889	1				
Import intensity with Russia	0.0126	0.8296	0.0742	0.0490	1			
Oil import from Russia	0.0710	0.0409	-0.0836	-0.0808	0.1109	1		
FDI from Russia	0.0350	0.0370	-0.1251	-0.2132	0.0152	0.4276	1	
Per capita GDP	0.0132	-0.0662	-0.1192	-0.2840	-0.1055	0.3362	0.5500	1

Given the high number of factors potentially influencing the voting behaviour, we test the relevance of both continuous and categorical variables by running respectively t-test and Chi-square test (Table 5). Both tests confirm there are significant means differences across countries that approved the resolution, countries that rejected it, and countries who stayed neutral. More specifically, most of the selected explanatory variables show significant differences across the three country groups. We show two sets of tests: one between the group that approved the resolution ($j=0$) and the rest of the countries combined ($j=1,2$), and one between the two country groups in favour of Russia ($j=1$ and $j=2$). In both cases we find significant differences in many factors at their means, as shown in Tables 5. We therefore proceed with model specification as follows.

¹² There is no alternative option other than approving, rejecting, or being neutral (either by abstaining or by being absent). Therefore, there is no need to test for the Independence of Irrelevant Alternatives (IIA), which makes the multinomial logit model well suited as estimation strategy.

4.3 Model specification

We estimate three different models. In all models the baseline case is Approve ($j=0$), which corresponds to vote in favour of Ukraine. Compared to that baseline, we estimate the probabilities that countries opt for other votes, i.e. Neutral ($j=1$) or Reject ($j=2$).

In Model 1, which is the full model, votes are grouped into three groups: $j=0$ for Approve, $j=1$ for Neutral and $j=2$ for Reject. Then, as the size of the group rejecting the resolution is very small (7 countries), we estimate two alternative models as a robustness check.

In Model 2, votes are grouped into two groups: $j=0$ for Approve and $j=1$ for all votes not in favour of Ukraine, including Neutral and Reject. Therefore, the results show the factors influencing the overall probability that a country did not vote in favour of Ukraine.

Finally, in Model 3, UN vote is 0 for Approve and 1 for Neutral in Ukraine resolution (abstain or absent), while votes against Ukraine resolutions are dropped. Therefore, the results show the factors influencing the probability that a country was neutral in Ukraine resolution.

Table 5 Variable selection

Category	Subgroup	Variable	Mean (% dbu for categorical variables)			Ttest ^a (Chi2 ^b)	
			Approve ($j=0$)	Neutral ($j=1$)	Reject ($j=2$)	$j=1$ vs $j=2$	$j=1+2$ vs. $j=0$
Economic influence	Trade ties with Russia	Export to Russia	1.11	2.56	6.77	**	n.s.
		Import from Russia	2.13	6.56	10.2	**	n.s.
		Oil imports from Russia 2017-21	113811	97660	11722	**	n.s.
		Arms imports from Russia	186	886	294	*	*
		FTA with Russia	(0.03)	(0.20)	(0.29)	**	**
	Trade ties with China	Export to China	9.44	16.77	17.29	**	n.s.
		Import from China	14.45	18.54	26.6	**	n.s.
	Investment relations with Russia	FDI from Russia	1904	166	697	**	**
BIT		(0.33)	(0.33)	(0.28)	n.s.	n.s.	
Defence cooperation		SCO member	(0.05)	(0.27)	(0.29)	**	**
		DCA with Russia	(0.16)	(0.58)	(0.57)	**	**
		NATO membership	(0.22)	(0)	(0)	**	n.s.
Soft power		BRI	(0.66)	0.89)	0.57)	**	**
		Global South	(0.63)	(0.89)	(0.71)	**	**
		Russian aid	0.03	0.13	0.43	**	n.s.
Host country controls		Per capita GDP	16636	3560	3011	**	n.s.
		Landlocked	(0.16)	(0.38)	(0.29)	**	**

a **significance at the 1% level, * significance at the 5% level. b significance at the 5% level.

4.4 Results

Table 6 presents the drivers of votes in favour of Russia in Ukraine UN resolution A/RES/ES-11/6. Among economic factors, we find empirical evidence in favor of the hypothesis that countries' voting was mostly influenced by countries' imports from Russia (especially arms imports, while oil imports are a significant but negative factor, due to major oil importers from Russia before 2022 were Western countries, including NATO members). Imports and specifically arms imports from Russia have positively influenced the probability to vote in favour of Russia, and this is consistent across different models. In Model 1 where Rejections and Neutrality are distinguished, the importance of imports and arms imports

from Russia for the group of countries who voted in favour of Russia is much higher. The same is true for the presence of FDI from Russia, a very influential factor in countries that voted in favour of Russia, unlike in the other countries. Among economic factors, trade with China, measured by either export or import trade intensity, is not significant in explaining the UN voting on Ukraine. Neither are the presence of institutional agreements with Russia in the form of Bilateral Investment Agreements (BIT), while the presence of a Free Trade Agreement (FTA) is.

Among non-economic factors, both defence cooperation with Russia and BRI membership influenced the odds of not voting in favour of Ukraine. When distinguishing between rejections and neutrality in Model 3, it seems that the latter was mostly driven by belonging to the Global South, while direct support of Russia was driven by a sizable amount of FDI from Russia received in the recent past.

Our results are partly consistent with previous research showing the relevance of trade ties with Russia also in votes at the UNGA on resolution (A/RES/ES-11-1) on March 2, 2022 demanding that Russia “immediately, completely and unconditionally withdraw all of its military forces from the territory of Ukraine within its internationally recognised borders” (Farzanegan & Gholipour, 2023). Moreover, we find important hard and soft power factors at work, including defence cooperation and foreign aid from Russia, together with a *prima facie* evidence of China’s influence through its BRI framework and Global South, which significantly influenced neutrality in voting patterns.

5 Conclusions

This paper has ventured into a recent fascinating avenue of research aimed at assessing different channels of international influence. Our paper contributes with an empirical analysis of a specific event - UN resolution A/RES/ES-11/6 so-called Ukraine resolution on March 2 2023 – as a case-study of the impact of different channels of international influence: economic, military, diplomatic. On the latter issue, progress is slow partly due to the major bilateral data requirement when measuring a country’s soft power impact on individual foreign countries. Our results suggest that economic, strategic and military influence by Russia in many countries, most frequently among the poorest in the world were pretty effective in securing political support in the UNGA on Ukraine resolution on March 2 2023. Arms imports, Russian aid and defence cooperation are the most important factors explaining voting behaviour in UN resolution A/RES/ES-11/6. At the same time, soft power initiatives by China have cemented a broad consensus within the Global South towards voting preferences aligned with the two big powers in the group. Although very small, the group of countries that rejected the resolution, i.e. voted explicitly in favour of Russia, are those that sum up many of the conditions that favour pro-Russia vote.

In the vast scholarship on soft power, within the international politics literature there is growing need to improve both conceptualisation and measurement of soft power (Seong-Hun, 2018). It goes beyond the aim of this paper to venture into the conceptualisation type of studies. We group some factors under the broad category of ‘Soft power’ in order to compare their impact to the categories including ‘Hard power’ tools such as economic and military ties. Future research should expand our operational category of ‘Soft power’ to include more factors in the realm of bilateral diplomatic, cultural and historical relations, provided they are measurable at bilateral level for the majority of world countries.

Table 6 Drivers of votes in favour of Russia UN resolution A/RES/ES-11/6

	Model 1		Model 2	Model 3
	0 = pro-Ukraine 1 = neutral 2 = pro-Russia		0 = pro-Ukraine 1 = pro-Russia & neutral	0 = pro-Ukraine 1 = neutral
Economic influence	1	2		
Export share to Russia	0.370 (1.88)	-10.751 (18.40)**	0.356 (1.87)	0.370 (1.88)
Export share to China	-0.025 (1.27)	-9.101 (36.06)**	-0.030 (1.50)	-0.025 (1.27)
Import share from Russia	0.953 (2.66)**	0.824 (2.26)*	0.979 (-2.71)**	0.953 (2.66)**
Import share from China	-0.014 (0.31)	-4.521 (19.34)**	-0.016 (0.37)	0.970 (0.64)
Arms import from Russia	0.001 (2.09)*	0.072 (30.91)**	0.001 (2.16)*	0.001 (2.09)*
Oil import from Russia	-2.372 (2.24)*	-15.964 (22.03)**	-2.479 (2.33)*	-2.372 (2.24)*
FDI from Russia	-0.002 (1.26)	0.029 (23.58)**	-0.002 (1.25)	-0.002 (1.26)
FTA	-	-	15.756 (10.59)**	15.891 (10.53)**
Per capita GDP	-0.000 (1.84)	-0.025 (20.04)**	-0.000 (1.88)	-0.000 (1.84)
Land-locked country	1.150 (1.19)	158.667 (27.01)**	1.048 (1.12)	1.150 (1.19)
Defence cooperation				
DCA	2.811 (3.26)**	110.239 (30.94)**	2.852 (3.29)**	2.811 (3.26)**
SCO	-0.545 (0.44)	-906.864 (31.23)**	-0.653 (0.50)	-0.545 (0.44)
Soft power				
Aid from Russia	1.377 (1.17)	267.669 (32.75)**	1.732 (1.62)	1.377 (1.17)
BRI	3.751 (2.67)**	114.637 (32.64)**	3.804 (2.81)**	3.751 (2.67)**
Global South	16.296 (2.80)**	225.271 (33.61)**	16.472 (2.84)**	16.295 (2.79)**
Pseudo R ²	0.6813	0.6813	0.6287	0.6099
Prob>chi ²	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
Countries		152	151	147

**significance at 1% level, * significance at 5% level. t-Statistics are in parentheses.

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